

FEATURES OF TREATMENT AND SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH INCOMPLETE SUICIDES

PhD, N. N. Djuraev

Andijan State Medical Institute, Department of psychiatry, narcology and medical psychology with a course of psychotherapy, Andijan, Republic of Uzbekistan

A. E. Malikova

Senior Lecturer, Andijan State Medical Institute, Department of psychiatry, narcology and medical psychology with a course of psychotherapy, Andijan, Republic of Uzbekistan

K. I. Fahriddinovna

Assistant, Andijan State Medical Institute, Department of psychiatry, narcology and medical psychology with a course of psychotherapy, Andijan, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: Suicide is a strong psychotraumatic factor, after which psychopathological disorders develop. As a result of a clinical and psychological examination of 210 patients (man-76, 36.2%; women-134, 63.8%) with incomplete suicides, different variants of asthenic, phobic, depressive states were most often observed. All patients were divided into two groups. The first group of 140 patients: the main one - these are patients who received a complex of drug therapy (antidepressants, tranquilizers). The second group of 70 patients: control - those who received antidepressants and tranquilizers and psychotherapy. The effectiveness of medical care for incomplete suicides was significantly higher in the first group of patients.

Keywords: suicide, personality, premorbid, character, accentuation.

Relevance: Suicidology is currently one of the topical sections of modern psychiatry [1,2]. This is due to the fact that suicides occupy the first place among the mortality of the population. In recent years, the COVID-19 virus pandemic has affected the increase in the frequency of suicide attempts due to the enormous moral and material damage that the problem of suicide causes to society [16]. More than 1 million people worldwide commit suicide every year.

In most cases, in many states, suicide continues to be one of the most acute medical and social problems [8,5]. According to modern concepts, the genesis of suicidal behavior involves a combination of various factors - biological, personal-psychological, social-environmental, ethnocultural, stressful, psychopathological, which allows us to consider suicidology as a multidisciplinary field of knowledge [12]. The problem of providing medical and psychological assistance to persons who have made a suicidal attempt is relevant in our time [7,18]. Over the past 45 years, the total number of suicides has increased by 60%, and currently about a million people per year die in this way [4]. In developed countries (USA, UK, Germany, etc.), suicide ranks third among the causes of death among the most able-bodied population after cardiovascular and oncological diseases [11,20]. The problem of suicide among adolescents is also acute,

since among people aged 15–19 years, suicide is the third cause of death among girls and the fourth among boys [15]. Despite the fact that prevention plays a significant role in the prevention of suicidal behavior, it remains important to provide direct medical and psychological assistance to persons who have attempted suicide [13,17]. The unflagging attention of specialists is attracted by studies of the mental health of suicides [9,10]. According to some authors, among suicides, persons with non-psychotic forms of mental disorders predominate, who, after committing a suicide attempt, are usually not hospitalized in a psychiatric hospital and remain without timely provision of psychiatric care [3,19]. According to other data, patients with schizophrenia and personality disorders predominate among those hospitalized after a suicide attempt, and in almost half of them, the underlying mental illness was complicated by alcohol or drug addiction [14]. Recently, most researchers regard depressive disorders as the most common and dominant cause of suicide [6].

Purpose of the study: To study the socio-psychological characteristics and psychopathological picture of patients with incomplete suicides, as well as the effectiveness of sedative therapy and including psychotherapy for emergency care in them.

Materials and methods. To solve the tasks set, the persons who came out after a suicidal fate in the toxicological, burn, neuro-reanimation and surgical departments of the Andijan branch of the RCEM were restored. We studied 210 patients with incomplete suicides. Of these, only 2 repeated suicidal news. According to statistics, 210 suicides who committed crimes that did not occur in dispensary observation. The control group consists of 50 persons (healthy people - volunteers, workers, employees, students). The examination of suicides was carried out by clinical-psychological, pathopsychological, anamnestic and clinical-catamnestic methods.

Results and discussions. The results showed that the analysis of suicidal attempts in the patients examined by us, as well as the suicidal behavior of most of them, was associated with the impact of real objectively and subjectively severe psychotraumatic environmental factors that cause frustration of the vital needs of the individual and its socio-psychological maladaptation.

Diagram 1. Distribution of examined persons depending on sex.

Not to mention the gender differences in suicides. Despite socio-cultural, economic and geographical differences, the incidence of suicide among men worldwide is significantly higher than among women. In general, the ratio of men to women in completed suicides is 4:1. According to our data, women (64.3%) attempted suicide more than men (35.7%). Many had an unsuccessful marriage, some were divorced. In such families there was no relationship, personal-family conflicts, insult, violence, betrayal by the husband. Among the examined persons in the control group, there were 17 (34.0%) men and 33 (66.0%) women.

Every minute someone attempts a deliberate suicide. These attempts 60 or 70 times a day are successful. The problem is getting worse as there is a significant increase in the number of suicide attempts and suicides among young people aged 20 to 25 years.

Diagram 2. Distribution of examined persons depending on age.

The age of the studied patients at the time of the examination ranged from 15 to 60 years. The bulk of the suicides of the examined population will be those who have reached adolescence: 114 patients (54.3%) were 15-20 years old, 30 (60.0%) of the examined persons were among the control group. Analysis of the age and sex characteristics of persons who made a suicide attempt shows the dominance of men in the age group of 21-30 years (10.0%), and women in the age group of 15-20 years (8.6%). Most often committed regardless of gender in the most able-bodied age from 15 to 30 years.

Our data confirm that relatives of suicide victims are at increased risk, both genes and environment contributing to this risk. Genetic predispositions in families are passed along with environmental risks, which forms a chain of interrelated events.

Genetic and constitutional - biological factors that increase the risk of suicidal behavior is a combination of hereditary burden of psychopathy and alcoholism (Popova N.M. 1997).

If there have already been cases of suicide in the family, this increases the risk of repeated suicide. Among the examined patients in their families there were cases of suicidal attempts (often the mother). The occurrence of such a factor as hereditary burden of mental disorders is especially high (41.8%) (respectively: 58.2 and 41.8%, $p < 0.05$). The largest share was occupied by unburdenedness in 58.2% of patients.

Premorbid personality traits, as one of the risk factors for auto-aggressive behavior, are studied quite deeply by both psychiatrists and psychologists and psychotherapists. A number of predisposing psychological and psychiatric factors of suicidal behavior have been identified, which include the following: increased tension of needs, desire for emotional intimacy, low ability to form psychological defense mechanisms, inability to reduce frustration, impulsiveness, explosiveness and emotional instability, increased suggestibility, uncompromisingness and lack of life experience, the presence of guilt and low self-esteem, hyporeactive emotional background during conflicts, difficulty in restructuring value orientations. In adolescence, the likelihood of auto-aggressive behavior largely depends on the type of character accentuation.

Numerous studies of the features of self-destructive behavior in various types of character accentuation in adolescents have made it possible to identify a risk group. The probability of auto-aggressive behavior is high with the following types of character accentuation.

According to our results, premorbid personality traits were found, without features in the main group were not noted, and the highest in the control group was 84.0%, premorbid features in the main group prevailed in hysteroid 22.3% and cyclothymic type 20.9%.

It should be noted that the main causes of suicide are family and microsocial factors. Peculiarities of upbringing, family type, vulnerability factors in the formation of personality were considered by us in a complex manner. Most of the suicides were unmarried and lived with their parents. Relations with family members were formal and poor.

According to our results, the professional affiliation of persons who have made suicidal attempts showed that they are most often observed in people with secondary education 143 (68.1%). Highly educated people are less likely to commit suicide 1 (0.5%). It should be noted that incomplete suicides are more often committed by people with low educational qualifications. Indicators of higher and incomplete higher among the control group 3 (6.0%) and 26 (52%).

Table 1. Distribution of suicides depending on the type of premorbid.

№	Premorbid	Main group n=210						Control group n=50						P
		Men		Women		Total		Men		Women		Total		
		Aбс	%	Aбс	%	Aбс	%	Aбс	%	Aбс	%	Aбс	%	
1	Without features	-	-	-	-	-	-	13	26,0	29	58,0	42	84,0	<0,001
2	Hyperthymic	14	6,7	12	5,7	26	12,4	2	4,0	-	-	2	4,0	<00,5
3	Cyclothym	13	6,2	31	14,7	44	20,9	-	-	-	-	-	-	<00,5
4	Labile	18	8,6	14	6,7	35	15,3	-	-	1	2,0	1	2,0	<00,5
5	Asthenoneurotic	5	2,4	6	2,9	11	5,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	<00,5
6	psychoasthenic	-	-	5	2,4	5	2,4	1	2,0	-	-	1	2,0	<00,5
7	Schizoid	9	4,3	7	3,3	12	7,6	-	-	-	-	-	-	<00,5
8	epileptoid	3	1,4	17	8,1	19	9,5	1	2,0	-	-	1	2,0	<00,5
9	hysterical	10	4,7	37	17,6	49	22,3	-	-	2	4,0	2	4,0	<00,5
10	Unstable	4	1,9	5	2,4	9	4,3	-	-	1	2,0	1	2,0	<00,5
	Total:	76	36,2	134	63,8	210	100,0	17	34,0	33	66,0	50	100,0	

Our common goal is to limit the spread of suicides as far as possible and learn how to effectively prevent them. However, this task is extremely difficult, since in order to solve it, it is necessary to achieve cardinal positive changes in social relations both at the macro- and at the micro-social levels.

When studying the psychopathological state of thematic patients after an incomplete suicide, various variants of the asthenic state were detected more often in 139 patients (66.1%), various variants of the depressive state in 45 patients (21.5%), a phobic state in 26 patients (12.4%).

Suicide after an incomplete suicide were in an unconscious state of stun, stupor, coma. They were provided with emergency assistance in the form of detoxification treatment, sedative treatment, antidepressants (amitriptyline, atarax, xel) and tranquilizers (sibazon, seduxen).

The use of these drugs in the form of intravenous administration turned out to be more effective, and later, after clarification of consciousness, psychotherapy (rational, hypnotherapy) was carried out.

Table 2. Evaluation of the effectiveness of treatment (number of bed-days)

№	Bed days	I group (receiving medical treatment)		II group (receiving medical treatment with psychotherapy)		Total		P
		Abs	%	Abs	%	Abs	%	
1.	4-6 days	19	13,6	58	82,9	77	36,7	<0,05
2.	6-8 days	121	86,4	12	17,1	133	63,3	<0,05
	Total	140	100,0	70	100,0	210	100,0	

Based on treatment outcome, we rated significant efficacy, moderate efficacy, and low efficacy. as effectiveness, we considered the reduction of psychopathological symptoms, bed-time savings, and repeated suicidal thoughts.

One of the main effectiveness of the treatment was the number of bed days provided, so in the second group who received a complex of drug therapy with psychotherapy, the number of days from 4 to a week was 82.9% compared to the first group. And the duration of stay from 6 to 8 days and more, on the contrary, is longer in the first group - 86.4%. Differences static reliable.

For the effectiveness of emergency care for incomplete suicides, all patients were divided into two groups. The first group of 140 (66.6%) patients: who received a complex of drug therapy without psychotherapy. The second group of 70 (33.4%) patients: patients who received a complex of drug therapy with psychotherapy.

With the improvement of the somatic condition of the patient, the degree of suicidal risk was determined and the issue of his discharge home or transfer to inpatient treatment in a neuropsychiatric dispensary was decided.

Diagram 3. Comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of treatment case patients

I-group
n=140
(receiving
drug treatment)

II-group
n=70
(receiving medication
treatment with psychotherapy)

Upon reaching the effectiveness of treatment in 70 examined patients (second group), antidepressants, tranquilizers and psychotherapy (rational, hypnotherapy) were prescribed. Of these, 66 (94.3%) recovered, significantly improved in 3 (4.3%), and slightly improved in 1 (1.4%) patients.

140 suicides (the first group) used antidepressants, tranquilizers. Of these, 15 (10.7%) patients recovered, significantly improved in 34 (24.3%) patients, and slightly improved in 91 (65.0%) patients.

Hypnotherapy was carried out in 70 examined patients aged 19 to 45 who were hospitalized.

Before the start of treatment, the patients underwent an explanatory and corrective psychotherapeutic conversation, and then ten sessions of hypnotherapy (in the III stage of hypnosis) lasting 40-45 minutes each. Particular attention in the selection of suggestion formulas was paid to complete relaxation and inducing a feeling of warmth, especially in the lower extremities. In addition, therapeutic formulas of suggestion were specially selected, aimed at the mental correction of the psychopathological disorders existing in patients and psychological preparation, aimed at increasing resistance to stress and activating compensatory mechanisms.

In the complex of this treatment, psychopathological symptoms quickly disappeared and the duration of treatment was shortened.

The leading feature of the provision of medical and psychological assistance to such patients is the complexity, including psychotherapeutic correction and drug treatment. In case of situational reactions, the psychotherapeutic impact is of paramount importance, aimed at providing patients with empathic support, deactualization of the conflict, mobilization of the patient's own psychological resources, correction of interpersonal relationships and, in general, rapid relief of the psychological crisis. In the future, our efforts were directed to the formation of new, more adaptive ways of personal response in situations that frustrate the leading needs of the individual, to increase tolerance to stress. Methods of individual and group therapy were of great importance.

Prevention of suicidal behavior.

1. Organization of psychological examination, identification of high-risk groups.
2. Organization of hotlines.
3. There should be a medical psychologist in every children's, school educational institutions and mahallas.
4. Dynamic monitoring of individuals at risk, periodic rational psychotherapy.

5. Increasing the number of doctors who know the methods of psychotherapy (at least rational) in all family clinics.

Conclusion: Suicide is a strong psychotraumatic factor, after which psychopathological disorders develop.

A significant role is played by the combination of hereditary burden (psychopathy and depression) with the presence in the premorbid of hyperthymic and unstable character traits in men, and hysteroid and emotive-labile in women.

In the treatment of thematic patients, complex therapy combined with psychotherapy is important, in particular, options for rational psychotherapy: family psychotherapy, hypnotherapy and autogenic training.

In the complex of this treatment, psychopathological symptoms quickly disappeared and the duration of treatment was shortened.

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